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ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING IN THE CONTEXT OF FORCED DISPLACEMENT

The war in Ukraine has caused a surge of students studying online from abroad. Under Russian aggression, learning has become a challenge for students and a daily test for teachers. The situation is particularly dire in frontline regions, where many educational establishments in the east and south were forced to switch entirely to remote learning for safety reasons (Tarasenko, 2025).

There are several studies dedicated to the problem of teaching refugees worldwide (H. A. Alrawashdeh, A. W. (Tony) Bates, N. Kunt, F. Menashi, Z. Zhakaria, etc.). The British Council carries out research and develops resources to support language learning in refugee education. The relevance of our study lies in the necessity to address the challenges Ukrainian teachers and students face nowadays. Thus, the aim of our research is to analyse the challenges Ukrainian teachers and displaced students face in online education and to review methods for teaching English online to displaced learners.

Displaced Ukrainian students abroad face different options for continuing their studies: some enrol in local education systems in the countries where they are staying; others remain affiliated with Ukrainian schools and universities and study online; some combine both. For this reason, English plays an important role in helping students keep up with their studies and connect to academic and professional opportunities abroad. However, displacement often creates significant challenges for learning. Differences in educational systems and the need to adapt to a new environment can negatively affect their learning progress. Furthermore, students experience stress due to the war and the move to another country. All this makes studying English harder.

Teachers play important roles in providing quality education to refugee students. Teachers are often unable to implement practices that meet refugee students' needs, such as trying new approaches or using different types of practices developed by researchers. That is why specialised training is needed to equip teachers with the skills and knowledge required to support refugee learners effectively (Alrawashdeh, Kunt, 2022).

Ukrainian teachers face specific pedagogical challenges when students study remotely from abroad. Teaching online requires constant adaptation to online formats, dealing with various technical limitations such as frequent power cuts, unstable Internet connections, device access, platform limitations, time-zone differences, and limited digital literacy. Moreover, teachers must continuously support students emotionally,

help them overcome stress and anxiety caused by the ongoing conflict and stimulate their motivation to study. Teachers need to design engaging tasks, provide interactive activities, give timely feedback and use online platforms and learning management systems (LMSs) to keep students involved and support their learning.

Depending on the circumstances, Ukrainian teachers combine synchronous and asynchronous forms of online education. Synchronous technologies require all participants in the communication to be together at the same time, but not necessarily in the same place. A video conference or a webinar is an example of synchronous technology that may be broadcast ‘live’, but not to everyone in the same place. Asynchronous technologies enable participants to access information or communicate at different times and places, usually at their convenience. All recorded media are asynchronous. Books, DVDs, YouTube videos, lectures recorded via lecture capture and available for on-demand streaming, and online discussion forums are all asynchronous media or technologies. Learners can log on or access these technologies at times and places of their choosing (Bates, 2015: 237).

Nowadays, more and more educational establishments use LMSs. LMSs are software that enable instructors and students to log in and work within a password-protected online learning environment. Most learning management systems, such as Blackboard, Desire2Learn and Moodle, are in fact used to replicate a classroom design model. They have weekly units or modules; the content is primarily text-based rather than oral (although increasingly video and audio are integrated into LMSs); the online discussion is mainly asynchronous rather than synchronous; and the course content is available at any time from anywhere with an Internet connection. Skilled teachers and instructors can modify or adapt LMSs to meet different teaching or learning requirements. (Bates, 2015, : 126–127).

Besides the technical and organisational issues, the psychological needs of displaced learners must also be taken into account. Refugees show greater needs for emotional and behavioural support than peers. The psychological status represented in anxiety and negative emotions prevents language acquisition or learning from occurring effectively. The traumatic events individuals experience indeed deeply and critically impact the brain (Alrawashdeh, Kunt, 2022). Acting as facilitators of learning and emotional recovery, teachers play a crucial role in supporting learners who experience trauma. Implementing trauma-informed practices can foster a sense of safety and stability among students. Teachers can achieve this by setting flexible deadlines, breaking complex tasks into smaller pieces, and providing activities that support students’ social and emotional development. In English language classes, it would be effective to introduce tasks such as vocabulary activities on emotions and well-being, pair discussions about feelings, role-plays of everyday situations, writing reflection journals on different topics, collaborative projects, teaching students to give positive feedback after their groupmates’ presentations, etc. These tasks are important for both language learning and psychological well-being. They help students develop

their communication skills, empathy and a sense of belonging. Thus, implementing these activities is crucial to their academic progress and emotional health.

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